

Supplementary Material:
**Prioritising Catchments for Nature Restoration for
Climate Change Adaptation.**

21st March 2025

verture

Summary

This Supplementary Material presents additional information to support the Prioritising Catchments for Restoration Report.

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Introduction

The purpose of this Supplementary Material is to provide additional information to inform discussions on the prioritisation of catchments for nature restoration to deliver climate adaptation outcomes. The purpose of the parent report is to present the findings of an integrated spatial analyses and stakeholder engagement process developed to identify candidate priority catchments in Scotland where Nature restoration can support the delivery of climate adaptation outcomes and deliver a range of multiple benefits.

Note: The following list of prioritisation criteria was developed through consultation with NatureScot, Verture and James Hutton Institute research staff. This is not an extensive list and has been developed to enable addition of further criteria and sub-criteria if of value for future further development. The list is not in any order of priority.

Table 1 (following pages). Primary criteria, sub-criteria list, importance indication and whether used in analysis.

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Primary criteria	Sub-criteria	Sub-criteria	Importance Red= low, amber= medium, green= high	Used in analysis Red= No Green= Yes Amber = 2 nd level	Notes
1. Reduce flood risk	1.1	Number of properties at risk			Total area of properties at risk have been included
	1.2	Where has already experienced severe flooding			Some flooding details but it is inconsistent and not national coverage
	1.3	Flood risk areas			Included (SM Figure 8 - SEPA PVA flood risk maps not directly used in WISE2 but used as a secondary level (properties at risk).
	1.4	Field Capacity Days / Maximum potential soil moisture deficit			Constraint maps from Land Capability for Agriculture are as yet unpublished
					Where the LCA changes under future climate scenarios (for secondary analysis)
	1.5	Peatland degradation - reduced water holding capacity in upper catchment			Included
	1.6	Wetland types with high potential for moderating flood risk			Separate material: Moderating extremes in water availability: a review of the role of functioning wetlands (https://www.crew.ac.uk/publication/moderating-extremes-water-availability-review-role-functioning-wetlands)
					Not included in prioritisation map but included in peatland map
1.7	Catchment area above flood risk receptor (main point of flooding)			Smaller sub-catchment areas could be better to target to have impact on flooding https://wires.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/wat2.1211 .	
1.8	Has it been identified by SEPA for NFM actions or works?			Not included - required data from SEPA (sought but not acquired). SEPA have reviewed which PVA catchments could be key priorities for NFM studies or actions.	
2. Reduce water scarcity risk	2.1	Catchments at risk of low flow			Hydrological (low flow) modelling using 2 model (GR6J, HYPE) at the outlets of 82 catchments (many nested, outlets at SEPA flow gauge locations) used by SEPA to conduct drought risk assessments. Drought modelling here refers to the process of calibrating river flows at the outlets, with a focus on low flows. This is done by using objective functions that give more weight to low flow conditions.
	2.2	Future Climatic Water Balance (P-ETo)			Included
	2.3	Use of hydrological drought metrics—drought frequency, duration			Data under future climate scenarios is included

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	2.4	Wetland types with high potential for moderating drought risk			Findings from CREW report: Moderating extremes in water availability: a review of the role of functioning wetlands: https://www.crew.ac.uk/publication/moderating-extremes-water-availability-review-role-functioning-wetlands
					Duplication of wetland types (in peatland prioritisation maps)
	2.5	SEPA abstraction datasets.			Total abstraction rates rather than points in an area. From HNC crucible and CREW project: Raw abstraction datasets at the water body level for different abstraction sectors provided by SEPA. Sectors include Agri Irri, Agri Non Irri, Distillery, Golf, Fish, Hydropower, Other Industrial/commercial
	2.6	Private Water Supply dataset.			Not included currently but could be integrated as additional analysis – Map of PWS sampled for water quality provided below. See also CREW Reports: https://www.crew.ac.uk/sites/www.crew.ac.uk/files/publication/CRW2022_05_Main_Report_and_Appendices.pdf and https://www.crew.ac.uk/publication/water-scarcity-impacts-distilleries-agricultural
3. Improve water quality	3.1	Areas of poor water quality			Not included as data not accessed. River segments of WFD poor water quality can be identified by SEPA datasets. Can be incorporated separately
	3.2	Soil leaching potential			Only available for, mainly cultivated, areas covered by the 1:25,000 Soil Map (partial-cover) (Soil Survey of Scotland Staff, 1970-1987). Gagkas and Lilly (2024)
	3.3	Nitrate runoff			Included
	3.4	Total Phosphorous loss			Dataset available for catchments that include Lochs, based on a CREW report. Not used as it requires expert input.
	3.5	Peat erosion & dissolved organic carbon			Included. Soil erosion risk class map is available for, mainly cultivated, areas covered by the 1:25k Soil map (partial-cover) (Soil Survey of Scotland Staff (1970-1987). Gap areas were filled using a disaggregated soil series map at 50m grid cell resolution (Gagkas and Lilly, 2024) translated to soil erosion risk classes.
	3.6	Pathways of diffuse pollution to waters			No data available (secondary - requires expert input). Findings from CREW report: A state of knowledge overview of identified pathways of diffuse pollutants to the water environment (https://www.crew.ac.uk/publication/state-knowledge-overview-identified-pathways-diffuse-pollutants-water-environment)
4. Reduced risks to infrastructure	4.1	Infrastructure mapping			WISE-2: Distance to nearest road, windfarms, buildings mapping. See Sub-criteria 1.1. None of the other infrastructure datasets have been integrated - issues around appropriate scaling

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5. Restoring resilient ecosystems	5.1				Partially included (see also Gimona and Castellazzi 2025)
6. Likelihood of getting investment in restoration	6.1				
7. Where restoration projects are already happening	7.1				Identified through stakeholder survey, key informant interviews, and climate risk disclosure reporting.
8. Improve benefits for biodiversity	8.1				Included via Gimona and Castellazzi 2025
Important salmon rivers	8.2				Agreed not to include
Special areas for conservation	8.3				Included as "designated sites"
Existing Riverwoods projects	8.4				Included in wider NS database of existing restoration projects
Target areas for riparian woodland	8.5				Potential to use RIVERTOOL and dataset from Scottish Forestry https://www.forestry.gov.scot/news-releases/boosting-tree-planting-around-rivers-and-streams
9. Climate change mitigation	9.1				Peatland restoration included; most (but not all) woodland included
10. Improvement in wellbeing and opportunities for recreation	10.1				Not included, as agreed
11. Improve soil health	11.1	Soil health Indicators			Work not at a stage to include. Research under way to develop a National Soil Monitoring Framework.
12. Peatland condition	12.1	Peatland Condition maps			Included
	12.2	Existing peatland restoration sites			Included
	12.3	Combination with Climatic Water Balance (Criteria 18)			Included
13. Groundwater recharge / geology	13.1	Low groundwater recharge rates			Not included, but see BGS maps to add narrative info: https://www.crew.ac.uk/sites/www.crew.ac.uk/files/publication/CRW2023_05_Intensive_Livestock_Infographic_FINAL.pdf
14. Stakeholder survey	14.1				Included
15. Water Quality: NVZ designation	15.1	Current NVZ catchments			Updates available of the national scale nitrate modelling (NIRAMS), so we have updated maps of nitrate leaching to groundwater for Scotland.

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					NVZs are designated based on SEPA's nitrate monitoring network (i.e. areas where nitrate concentrations exceed a maximum (50 mg/l) or mean (37.5 mg/l) threshold, or there is a risk they will do so). NIRAMS modelling is used as an additional strand of evidence to evaluate the degree of confidence in NVZ designation. Note that the spatial extent of NVZs are based on groundwater bodies (GWBs) defined by BGS and SEPA; these GWBs are assumed to be self-contained from the point of view of diffuse nitrate pollution. The NVZ map therefore just shows the (aggregated) GWBs that have been designated as NVZ/vulnerable to diffuse nitrate pollution.
					Included
16. Downstream flow length	16.1				Included. River lengths for 81 DRAT stations up to the downstream NRFA station
17. Topography (elevation/slope/aspect etc.)	17.1				Slope topography & growing season length
18. Future climate: Climatic Water Balance	18.1	Locations with higher water deficit			Included
	18.2	Locations with higher water surplus			Included
	18.3	Soils with low water holding capacity			Not included (although data available) - some methodological and interpretational challenges about actual impact on ecosystems
19. Future climate: extremes	19.1	Higher probability of consecutive dry days			Not included but available at: https://climatedata.hutton.ac.uk/index.html There are large spatial and temporal variations and between climate projections.
	19.2	Higher probability of heavy rain days			Not included but available at: https://climatedata.hutton.ac.uk/index.html There are large spatial and temporal variations and between climate projections.
20. Historical land use	20.1				Used in WISE2 for impact on the response of the soil to restoration practices
21. Practicalities of restoration: distance to roads / rural areas	21.1	Distance from where restoration required to access point			Included (part of WISE2 for peatland restoration assessment)
22. Land ownership	22.1	Single / multiple owners?			Distinction between owned and rented land included (owned land higher priority)
23. Erosion Risk: Water	23.1	Erosion risk map			Included. Available at 50m grid resolution for the area primarily covered by cultivated land in Scotland and adjacent uplands, shows the risk of a bare soil being eroded by water under intense or prolonged rainfall (Lilly and Baggaley, 2014). See also sub-criteria 3.5
24. Erosion Risk: Wind	24.1	Forested areas at risk			Not included (ongoing work on this at JHI)
	24.2	LCA class - erosion constraint			Arable areas at risk of wind erosion (ongoing work on this at JHI)

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					Not yet included in new LCA
25. Insurance costs	25.1	Blue line areas (uninsurable)			Not included - hard to access data
26. Identified need in existing climate adaptation plan	26.1				Included where available within Verture analysis
27. River basin management plans	27.1				Included where available within Verture analysis

References:

Gagkas, Z.; Lilly, A. (2024) Spatial disaggregation of a legacy soil map to support digital soil and land evaluation assessments in Scotland, Geoderma Regional, 38, Art. E00833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2024.e0083>

Lilly, A & Baggaley, N.J., 2014. Developing simple indicators to assess the role of soils in determining risks to water quality, CREW project number CD2012_42. Available online at: crew.ac.uk/publications www.crew.ac.uk/publications

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Restoration prioritisation data integration

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Purpose of the work

The decision to carry out restoration at a specific site depends on multiple factors, many of which are subjective and relate to the particulars of the site. In this project we have adapted earlier work to provide a framework of spatial datasets and weighting for calculating a score for prioritisation of restoration across Scotland. The aim of the work is to provide stakeholders with information for future decision-making on restoration, and also to provide information on where prioritisation scores will be consistently high regardless of which factors are considered more important than others. This work was carried out under the NatureScot Landscape Restoration project and aligns with JHI-C3-1 Supporting Scotland's Land Use Transformations, and the JHI-D3-2 CentrePeat project within the 2022-2027 Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division (RESAS) Strategic Research Programme.

The original WISE framework concept

Published in 2014 ([WISE booklet v2 Nov 2013 reduced size.pdf](#)), the original WISE concept was designed to provide a decision support tool for identifying where peatland restoration would be most desirable by a range of stakeholder groups. This framework produced a set of 100 metre resolution spatial datasets and explored stakeholder 'weighting' of each of the factors represented. The work was not able to produce some of the datasets that were identified as important in relation to restoration, due to data shortages and computational processing restrictions. The goal of the current work is to expand on the original WISE concept, with updated datasets and a framework for integrating and analysing these in a manner that goes beyond reliance on small numbers of stakeholders with very different opinions from one to another.

Datasets used

We used multiple spatial datasets, compiled from a range of sources and adjusted to provide normalised inputs to the framework model. A metadata table has been developed for each dataset (described below) with justification for why it was included and information on how the data was presented within the framework. Each dataset was normalised so that it had a minimum value of 0 and a maximum of 1. This was done to avoid having datasets with larger numerical ranges 'swamp' the score/summation process. Normalised datasets were reprojected where necessary to the OSGB 1936 projection, and resampled to 50 metre grid resolution.

Downstream impact: at each point identified as having peat, the total path length downstream was calculated. Values at each point were then divided by the maximum path length found across Scotland, to give a range of values between 0 and 1. This dataset was included because peatland in good condition has an impact on areas downstream of it, with improved water buffering and filtering, and mitigation of flood risk. Restoration at a point with a larger potential downstream impact might therefore be considered more important than at a point with no downstream impact.

Slope: steeper slopes have faster hydrological flow rates and greater erosion risk. We therefore assumed that flatter areas might have greater probability of success in post-restoration recovery. Values of slope (in degrees) were calculated at each point, and divided by the maximum. These values were then subtracted from 1 to give flat locations a value of 1 and steep locations a correspondingly lower value.

Land ownership type: we included this factor on the assumption that land managers who rented their land were less likely to invest in restoration or to spend time applying for funds to achieve this; the reasoning here was that with less confidence that they would continue to live at that location, they are less likely to make long-term investments in land management. Therefore, locations where private land ownership was identified were given a value of 1, and locations where land was rented were given a value of 0. Where land ownership was unknown, we defaulted to the 'private ownership' category.

Historical land use: soil properties are affected by land use. Historical land use impacts on soil may have declined over time, but may not have disappeared entirely. Using the historic land use map at the Historic Land-use Assessment project ([HLA](#)), we produced a map of historical land use 'intensity' based on expert judgement of the impacts of specific land use/land cover types. Less intense land use history gave each location a higher value, on the assumption that post-restoration recovery would be less affected under less intense historical land use conditions.

Site designations: we have assumed that if there is a designation with any effect in terms of environmental protection in place at a location, then it will be inherently easier to get planning approved for restoration work to be carried out on that location. We have combined maps of different types of designation across Scotland, to produce a map with 'designation' given a value of 1 and 'no designation' given a value of 0.

Distance to roads: transport of equipment and materials across rough and/or boggy terrain is difficult and expensive. Restoration sites that are near roads are therefore assumed to be favoured by practitioners. We have scored sites next to roads with a value of 1, and those further from the nearest road with a correspondingly lower value as the distance increases.

Agricultural payments: the values used in this dataset are derived from the level of Direct Agricultural Support Payment per hectare for 2022. This includes Basic Payment Scheme (BPS), Greening and Less Favoured Area Support Scheme (LFASS) payments. The assumption being made here is that restoration would lead to a loss or reduction in payments and so where payments are higher, there may be more reluctance to consider restoration. It is important to note that the dataset used does not always connect a payment rate to the exact piece of land for which the claim is appropriate but rather can include larger parcels of land within which the agricultural land use is contained.

Impact of future climate: derived from JHI analysis of the number of months when drought risk will increase under future climate, this dataset is used to indicate where restoration success may be affected by changing weather patterns across Scotland. Our assumption is that in places where this success rate is compromised by future climate, practitioners may prefer not to carry out restoration work.

Growing season length: vegetation recovery will depend on growing season length, with shorter growing seasons assumed to be less preferred for growth of vegetation as well as for other species. The dataset we used for this is Growing Season Length as defined by Matthews et al (2008) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3354/cr00751>, calculated using HADUK GRID observed interpolated gridded daily values at 1km over the period 1991-2020.

Windfarm development: if a windfarm development exists at a site of potential restoration, it is assumed that this will complicate access and the movement of equipment and materials. We have compiled GIS layers of known windfarm developments and given these a score of 0 in this layer, with other areas having a score of 1. This layer is one of several where further evidence may provide nuance, such as whether the contractor doing the restoration work is part of the same organisation as the windfarm owner/developer, or whether the developer has a stated goal of having restoration work carried out (in which case this could make restoration easier rather than harder to coordinate).

Erosion risk: Soil erosion risk class map is available at 50m grid cell resolution for, mainly cultivated, areas covered by the 1:25k Soil map (partial-cover) (Soil Survey of Scotland Staff (1970-1987). Gap areas were filled using a disaggregated soil series map at 50m grid cell resolution (Gagkas and Lilly, 2024) translated to soil erosion risk classes. Areas of high erosion risk are marked with 1, while areas of low erosion risk are marked with 0.

Nitrate Vulnerable Zones: designation of an area as an NVZ aims to reduce or prevent the pollution of water caused by the application and storage of organic and inorganic nitrogen fertiliser on agricultural land. By controlling land use management, the legislation aims to protect drinking water supplies, aquatic ecosystems and other legitimate uses of water. This dataset, from the Scottish Government GI-SAT (Geographic Information Science and Analysis Team) has been used with a value of 1 where an NVZ exists, and a value of 0 where it does not.

Soil runoff risk: The risk of the soil becoming saturated, causing water (or any liquid applied to the soil) to flow over land (runoff) and carry potential pollutants into water courses, or to collect (pond) on the surface. This dataset, derived from the Hydrology of Soil Types (HOST) classification (Lilly and Baggaley, 2014), has been normalised to have a value of 1 at the areas of highest runoff risk, and a value of 0 at the lowest runoff risk areas.

Randomised weightings

The fundamental concept behind this work is that each stakeholder involved in restoration (in any sense of involvement) will have specific priorities and will attach different importance to each factor for consideration when deciding where restoration should take place. In the original WISE work (Artz et al., 2014), multiple stakeholders were asked to provide weightings for a range of normalised factors similar to those used in the current work. The spatially explicit factors were then multiplied by each weighting, and the resultant weighted maps added together to give a final map of individualised prioritisation. Artz et al. found that there was significant variation between the maps generated for each set of stakeholder preference, making it difficult to identify areas where agreement on high priority of restoration could be reached.

Here we have generated 100 sets of random 'virtual stakeholder' weightings for each of the datasets/factors described above, and used these to create 100 maps of individual stakeholder restoration prioritisation. We have then calculated the mean prioritisation value at each location across these maps to explore whether there are areas where, regardless of stakeholder preference, the prioritisation 'score' is likely to be high. We have also calculated the variance in the prioritisation value, to show where prioritisation values tend to vary a lot or a little. This work involved a significant amount of spatial data computation, which was carried out using the JHI High Performance Computing system ([Supercharging science with high performance computing - James Hutton Institute](#)).

A final step is to clip mapped data to remove land cover types where restoration is inappropriate or unlikely to occur, for example urban areas, arable crop land and intensively grazed grassland. It is worth noting however that ecosystem restoration within these land cover types, e.g. riparian woodlands and or land use changes such as uptake of agroforestry, are compatible with the multiple benefit objectives of landscape restoration.

Additional Data Inclusion

A secondary level of spatial data consideration of criteria and prioritisation can then occur using additional data sets that are not suited to the WISE2 approach. This approach enables a combination of both a systematic method and individual data layers assessment. The ability to do this systematically and in detail per input data set has however been limited as they vary in their national coverage and due to resources constraints. Examples are provided below.

SM Figure 1 (Repeated from main report). Proposed priority catchments for nature restoration.

Interpreting the WISE 2 Normalised Score

To interpret the following normalised score Figure 3, those areas with the brightest yellow have a score of 1, meaning that they score highest across the range of criteria and have a high priority for restoration, whilst darker yellow / brown consistently have low scores hence lower priority for restoration.

SM Figure 3 (repeated from report) Normalised restoration priority score with areas where restoration is not currently feasible removed (i.e. arable, urban). Green dots indicate locations of existing Nature-based Solutions restoration projects identified in the survey, Blue dots are locations identified as at risk from threats.

SM Figure 4. Impact of water abstraction normalised score.

SM Figure 5. Designated sites (all types).

SM Figure 6. Agricultural payments normalised score. See Wise2 method description.

SM Figure 7. Site Access (distance from roads) normalised score.

SM figure 8. Areas of flood risk

SM Figure 9. Flow length normalised score for impact on downstream

SM Figure 10. Future climate change impact normalised score. See also SM Figures 23-2 and [The James Hutton Institute Climate Data Visualisation](#) for other climate indicators and summaries.

SM Figure 11. Growing season impact normalised score. Also see [The James Hutton Institute Climate Data Visualisation](#) for other relevant Agrometeorological Indicators.

SM Figure 12. Impact of historical land use. See Wise2 method description. HLA: [Historic Land-use Assessment](#)

SM Figure 13. Impact of historical land use. See Wise2 method description..

SM Figure 14. Nitrate Vulnerable Zones.

SM Figure 15. Land ownership (owned or rented). See WISE2 method description.

SM Figure 16. Normalised score for slope. See Wise2 method description.

SM Figure 17. Soil erosion risk

SM Figure 18. Normalised score for risk of soil runoff.

SM Figure 19. Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (UWWTD) sensitive catchments.

Additional spatial data to inform catchment prioritisation discussions.

The following maps and graphics are provided to facilitate further consideration of other factors not included in the prioritisation process.

SM Figure 20a. Peatland condition map. Developed using RESAS Strategic Research Programme projects C3 (Land Use Transformations) and D3-2 (CentrePeat).

Table 2. Areas of peat (hectares) by condition class (bare / eroding are highlighted) for proposed priority catchments.

Condition class	Leven (Fife)	Devon	Allan Water	Forth	Tweed	Doon	Ayr	Clyde	Deveron	Don	Dee (Grampian)	South Esk	Tay	Earn	Spey
Flooded	13	62	3	1756	134	690	179	246	2	4	133	25	4400	253	399
Settlement	105	103	22	382	109	287	335	568	36	40	48	20	367	130	299
Industrial extraction	42	0	0	69	23	0	0	273	87	0	0	0	0	0	23
Domestic extraction	3	0	0	0	0	0	224	21	342	7	55	0	8	0	115
Forest/woodland	1403	1204	1686	13681	15385	6850	6476	16477	3538	1195	2402	806	21075	2848	13021
Arable cropland	88	31	80	386	44	2	11	8	93	66	156	2	77	53	25
Intensive grassland	120	32	147	700	394	109	1005	3751	414	104	93	68	687	136	442
Extensive grassland	0	0	0	0	0	0	53	34	0	0	0	0	2	0	1
Bare/eroding modified drained	0	1	150	222	1148	15	510	634	474	173	206	56	1516	272	550
Bare/eroding modified undrained	27	516	603	3451	6336	151	1503	2982	2220	2114	11019	2633	21023	2426	22684
Molinia dominated drained	3	47	153	370	282	467	2901	4864	1	0	19	0	2347	299	5
Molinia dominated undrained	121	2629	1210	3558	4661	2056	3680	7113	10	8	1124	0	8965	2955	1512
Heather dominated drained	7	5	417	473	1697	322	1385	2857	2202	781	2015	500	10831	1112	4292
Heather dominated undrained	131	112	1637	7995	8087	3224	2266	6566	5432	7739	32458	4691	82342	9174	57423
Grass dominated drained	0	1	5	30	0	4	140	45	0	0	20	1	173	6	72
Grass dominated undrained	16	3	14	820	14	61	230	196	8	1	958	54	2359	43	2593
Sedge/rush dominated drained	2	4	7	23	10	5	74	66	5	3	1	4	118	23	7
Sedge/rush dominated undrained	66	28	56	556	171	99	155	218	216	32	127	39	1289	88	322
Near natural bog	39	461	776	2421	1117	1421	1718	3342	171	20	1424	216	12415	1074	6223
Near natural fen	0	0	0	21	0	0	15	14	0	0	2	5	106	0	7
Rewetted bog	0	0	40	84	337	0	26	97	21	114	763	29	553	62	2199
Other modified peatland	131	365	562	1748	1649	816	1292	1418	143	86	2717	112	18065	1817	6954

SM Figure 20b. National Forest Inventory (2023).

SM Figure 21 UK-CEH Land Cover Map (left) and Space Intelligence SLAM-MAP habitat maps of Scotland

SM Figure 22. Existing riparian woodland (NatureScot data).

NatureScot (2023) Riparian Woodland Scotland.

<https://spatialdata.gov.scot/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/ac10398e-a9ec-427f-bd9f-116582e95c0d>

"Riparian woodland in Scotland identified using a combination of existing open datasets. Search area is 20m either side of water courses. Includes coniferous and broadleaved woodland, native and non-native."

Climate Projections

Change direction agreement for mean monthly precipitation over the period 2020-2049 for at least 12 ensemble members

Change direction agreement for mean monthly precipitation over the period 2050-2079 for at least 12 ensemble members

SM Figure 23. Agreement maps for all 12 UKCP18 climate projections on the direction of change in mean monthly precipitation for the 2020 – 2049 (top) and 2050 – 2079 (bottom) periods, compared to the 1960-1989 baseline.

SM Figure 23 shows the agreement in either having an increase or decrease in precipitation for 12 climate projections (UKCP18). This approach provides more confidence in the probabilities of estimated future climates. There is general agreement for most of Scotland that September may experience a decrease in precipitation. Similarly, February is likely to see an increase. Yellow areas in represent locations where there is no agreement between the projections (e.g. some indicate increases, other decreases). For January, there are few areas where there is agreement for the 2020 – 2049 period, but this shifts towards agreement that southern Scotland is likely to see an increase in precipitation.

It is worth noting that the level of agreement between projections increases in the 2050 – 2049 period for some months, e.g. the ‘uncertain’ (yellow) areas in August and September in Figure 23 are less than for the 2020 – 2049 period, but decreases for others (e.g. June).

Climatic Water Balance (Precipitation – Evapotranspiration)

SM Figure 24. Changes in direction of mean monthly Climatic Water Balance (Precipitation – Evapotranspiration). Top: changes between 1960-198 baseline) and 1990-2019; Middle and bottom: example of changes from baseline and projected 2020-249 and baseline and 2050-2079, respectively (UKCP18 no. 04). Change direction: dark red = surplus to deficit; light red = deficit to deficit; dark blue = deficit to surplus; light blue = surplus to surplus.

SM Figure 25. Climatic Water Balance Ratio for the period 1990-2019 (left) and an example estimated using the UKCP18 (projection 04) for the 2020-2049 period.

SM Figure 24 shows the changes in the Climatic Water Balance indicator (CWB), which is the difference between precipitation and reference evapotranspiration (ET_0). This can be used to indicate whether a location may experience a shift from water surplus to deficit, or deficit to surplus.

The Climatic Water Balance ratios (CWR) provides more information in respect of the quantity of water, and is defined as the ratio of Precipitation (P) to (ET_0):

$$CWB \text{ ratio} = \frac{P}{ET_0}$$

This approach can be used to both identify surpluses and deficits; $CWR \geq 1$ denote climatic water surpluses while $CWR < 1$ denote climatic water deficits, but it also provides the magnitude of these surpluses or deficits; for example, CWR value above 2 indicates a strong or extreme climatic water surplus because precipitation is two times higher than evapotranspiration.

SM Figure 21 uses the following four classes of CWR levels: $CWR < 0.5$: Severe climatic water stress, precipitation covers 50% of the evapotranspiration demand); CWR between 0.5 and 1 (moderate climatic water stress); CWR between 1 and 2 (moderate climate water surplus); and $CWR > 2$ ('extreme' climatic water surplus).

For further details see: <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Assessment-of-Natural-Capital-asset-exposure-to-current-and-future-meteorological-drought-Report-D21d-D23c.pdf>

SM Figures 24 and 25 are available for other UKCP18 climate projections.

These CWR layers have been used to assess the exposure of upland blanket peat to observed (1990 - 2019) and future (2020 - 2049) meteorological drought and to assess potential effects on water table levels in relation to regulation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. (Gagkas et al., 2024). Areas of peat soil were derived from a digital soil map of Scotland (Gagkas and Lilly, 2024) translated to Hydrology of Soil Types (HOST) class 29 (Upland Blanket Peat), and covered 10,624 km² (or ~14% of Scotland's area). Exposure was assessed by spatially overlaying the HOST class 29 map with monthly data layers of CWR calculated using 1 km interpolated gridded observed climatic data and UKCP18 climate projection daily climatic data for the 'high emissions' scenario (RCP8.5). A single future climate scenario, Ensemble Member 5 (EM05), was used, which represents a drier climatic scenario compared to the baseline period (1960 - 1989) in terms of mean annual precipitation.

Based on this analysis, a mapping assessment was conducted to identify areas of upland blanket peat under continuous climatic water deficits (based on observed and future monthly CRW averages) for the May to August (Scenario 1 (S1)) and the April to September (Scenario 2 (S2)) periods (SM Figures 26 and 27, respectively). This analysis found that for the observed period (1990 - 2019), 2,460 km² (~20% of the upland blanket peat area) was exposed to continuous water stress in the May to August period (S1), and only a small area (13 km²) in the April to September period (S2). However, when the EM05-based future climate (2020 - 2049) was considered, upland blanket peat soil areas under continuous water deficit from May to August and from April to September greatly increased to 7,851 km² and 4,027 km², respectively, representing 74% and 38% of all areas, respectively. These comprised of extensive areas of upland blanket peat in the Flow County, the Isle of Lewis, the Cairngorms, and the Southern Uplands, that were projected to be in continuous water stress based on one plausible future climate for S1, with the exception of peat areas in northwestern Highlands, the Isle of Skye, and the Isle of Mull (SM Figure 26). Peat soil areas under continuous climatic water stress for the longer period from April to September were mainly found in the eastern part of Scotland (SM Figure 27).

SM Figure 26. Maps of Upland Blanket Peat (HOST class 29) based on Scenario 1: Continuous climatic water deficit from May to August, for the observed (1990 – 2020) period and future (2020 – 2049) period for Ensemble Member (EM) 05.

SM Figure 27. Maps of Upland Blanket Peat (HOST class 29) based on Scenario 2: Continuous climatic water deficit from April to September, for the observed (1990 – 2020) period and future (2020 – 2049) period for Ensemble Member (EM) 05.

In periods of climatic water surpluses and if there is potential for storage in the peat's saturation zone, the distance from the surface of the soil to the water table can potentially be reduced, with potential positive effects related to the reduction of GHGs emissions. However, prolonged climatic water deficits could lead to further depletion of water in the water table that may favour the release of GHGs from the surface soil layer.

Eroded and degraded peat is more vulnerable to climatic water deficits. Prevention of methane emissions by Sphagnum covering ponds may become reduced if they dry out. Therefore, these results highlighted the importance of restoring and/or maintaining bogs in good condition (i.e., fully saturated) because this can maintain and/or improve the resilience of peat soils to climatic water deficits and improve the provision of their climate regulation services.

This analysis was based on the climatic projections of a single Ensemble Member (EM05), considered to represent more prolonged dry conditions, but not necessarily the most intense dry ones. Moreover, the results presented here are the means for the period, hence do not represent the extreme individual years. Using a different climate projection would alter the magnitude of climatic water balance shifts presented here, and hence the levels of exposure; however, there is strong agreement between

different projections with regards to the direction of change in climatic water balance in Scotland. This provides confidence in the assumption that can be made based on the findings of this analysis.

Climatic Water Balance References:

Gagkas Z., Jabloun M., Rivington M., Aitkenhead, M. (2024). Deliverable 2.2a Climate change effects on soil properties and functions: the case of soil water balance. The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen. Scotland. <https://zenodo.org/records/11210904>

Gagkas, Z., Lilly, A. (2024) Spatial disaggregation of a legacy soil map to support digital soil and land evaluation assessments in Scotland, Geoderma Regional, 38, Art. E00833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2024.e00833>

Nitrogen concentrations

SM Figure 28. Average Nitrogen Concentration (mg/l) in water courses estimated using the NIRAMS model for the period 2015-2020 at a 1km resolution.

SM Figure 29. Average Nitrogen Concentration (mg/l) in Groundwater Bodies (GWB) estimated using the NIRAMS model for the period 2015-2020.

Drought metrics computed using observed discharge data (RESAS D2-1 WP1)

A dataset of observed daily flow values for 81 hydrometric river level stations, examined for 1991-2020, to identify drought events. Every hydrometric river station had an associated Q95 threshold, which was calculated from the 5th percentile of flow levels for that station during the period 1991-2020. The DRAT methodology assesses five-day mean flow levels for each station and when that value falls below the Q95 threshold, this is deemed low flow. After 30 consecutive days of low flow (below Q95 threshold), the station and its catchment area are said to be in significant water scarcity (drought event).

Reference: Glendell M, Schurch N., Frantsuzova A., Butler A., Naha S., Gagkas Z., Adams A. and Macleod K. (2023). Exploring the sensitivity of the Drought Risk Assessment Tool as part of the National Water Scarcity Plan Review in Scotland. The James Hutton Institute and Biomathematics and Statistics Scotland, Aberdeen, UK.

1. Drought Frequency (Number of drought counts (events)/year) at 81 DRAT sites

SM Figure 30. Drought frequency at 81 DRAT sites under scenario- 5 daily mean flow threshold falling below threshold Q95 computed for 30 years in historical period 1990-2020

2. Median Average Drought Durations (days) - Median of average drought duration values for each drought event

SM Figure 31 Drought Durations at 81 DRAT sites under scenario- 5 daily mean flow threshold falling below threshold Q95, computed for 30 years in historical period 1990-2020

Potential drought frequency and durations based on modelled discharge and reported water use data at 23 catchments in Scotland (HNC/CREW project)

Reference: Miriam Glendell, Kirsty Blackstock, Kerr Adams, Jack Brickell, Jean-Christophe Comte, Zisis Gagkas, Josie Geris, David Haro, Mohamed Jabloun, Alison Karley, Laure Kuhfuss, Kit Macleod, Shaini Naha, Eleanor Paterson, Mike Rivington, Chloe Thompson, Kirsty Upton, Mark Wilkinson, Kirsten Williams (2024). *Future predictions of water scarcity in Scotland: impact on distilleries and agricultural abstractors*. CRW2023_05. Centre of Expertise for Waters (CREW).

The drought profiling framework was adapted from an existing study to calculate the volume of water available after abstraction in 23 catchments with available abstraction (reported water use data) and modelled discharge data. Low flow events were defined as periods when the volume of available water, following actual abstraction, fell below the long-term Q95 threshold (i.e. flow that occurs less than 5% of the time). Following the drought definition from Scotland National Water Scarcity Plan (SEPA, 2020), we defined drought as an event when flow was below Q95 for 30-days or longer. We then calculated the frequency and duration of drought events for all scenarios across 23 catchments with available data. Frequency was defined as a number of droughts/year whilst Duration is a measure of the average event duration in days.

We found an increase in mean, minimum and maximum frequency and drought duration between the baseline (2007 – 2018) and future periods (2019 – 2050). Mean drought frequency increased from 0.33 to 0.65, while average drought duration increased from 31 to 51 days across the 23 study catchments. Up to 25% increase in historical abstractions is not anticipated to significantly affect future water availability across catchments in Scotland. Therefore, the observed increase in future drought duration and frequency can be primarily attributed to the hydrological model projections of decreased future flows.

SM Figure 32 Drought frequency extracted from the drought profiling framework for the (left) historical period (2007–2018) driven by Grid-to-Grid (G2G) hydrological model simulated flows using RCM (Regional Climate model projections) and baseline abstractions (right) future (2019–2050) using G2G projected flows and baseline abstractions (reported water use data). Catchments in white were not included in the analysis due to lack of data. (0.1=1:10 years; 0.2=1:5 years; 0.5=1:2 years; 1=1 a year; 2= 2 a year)

SM Figure 33. Average drought duration (in days) extracted from the drought profiling framework for the (left) historical period (2007 – 2018) driven by (Grid-to-Grid hydrological model) G2G model simulated flows using RCM (regional climatic projections) and baseline abstractions (right) future (2019 – 2050) using G2G projected flows and baseline abstractions (reported water use data). Catchments in white were not included in the analysis due to lack of data.

Private water supply locations

Reference: Pawar, S.K. (2024) 'Assessing the impact of Meteorological Droughts on Water Security in Scotland's Private Water Supplies', PhD thesis, University of Dundee.

SM Figure 34. Map indicating locations of Private Water Supplies sampled for water quality from 2006-2018 in Scotland with roughly 34,000 sites.

Existing Initiatives (April 2024)

SM Figure 35. Existing Adaptation Partnerships in Scotland and their stage of maturity.

Stakeholder Survey and Interviews

SM Figure 36. Locations where survey respondents identified climate risks. The colours relate to the respondent type / sector. Red - Public body/agency; Blue – Local Authority; Purple – landowner; Green – NGO; Yellow – Rivers Trust

The locations of identified climate risks (SM Figure 36) and nature restoration projects in progress (SM Figure 37) provided by the survey respondents were mapped as far as possible using GoogleMyMaps. This data was made compatible with GIS by converting the longitude and latitude information from the survey respondents to a 12 fig grid ref from Ordnance Survey. The outputs of this were layered onto the GIS map to provide a shared perspective of climate risk, both from a scientific data perspective, and from reflections and experiences of organisations and people on the ground.

* Catchments identified in key informant interviews related to climate risk or areas of proposed or active nature based solution projects were not represented as data points in the spatial maps as they were collated and shared with project partners after the spatial maps were created by JHI. They include climate risks identified in the Clyde (NHS Scotland Assure), the Dee (Scottish Water) and the Forth (Network Rail). This emphasises that the published report serves as a foundation for further conversation with infrastructure providers as a next step.

SM Figure 37. Locations that survey respondents identified that nature restoration projects were already being progressed. Again, colours are representative of respondent type / sector: Purple – Public body / agency; Black – Local Authority; Blue – Landowner; Orange – NGO.

Key caveats for the stakeholder maps

The maps produced of the locations identified through qualitative research are not necessarily wholly accurate, as exact locational data was rarely provided. Instead, they provide a relative distribution of the interpretation of climate risk and nature-based activities to mitigate impacts of those risks from diverse perspectives including NGOs, local authorities, public bodies/agencies and landowners.

The survey data overlay lacks consistency in scale, as locations provided by respondents varied from catchment names to individual sites. In addition, the sample lacks contributions from groups like landowners, several local authorities and infrastructure providers and NGOs/groups known to be delivering nature restoration projects. For many responses, risks were challenging to deduce to single locations. This variance should be considered when interpreting the maps. During follow up conversations on progressing nature restoration, the supplementary data from the survey outputs covering risk and project type as well as descriptive locational information should be used to inform a participatory approach to landscape scale restoration. We recommend NatureScot own this dataset and continues to contribute points of recognised climate risk and known nature-based solutions projects

While rich in information and context that has been shared with NatureScot, the interviews with key informants were limited in pinpointing specific locations of climate risk and adaptation strategies. For

many, attempts to associate risk with specific places and assets was an ongoing endeavour. Once priority catchments have been identified and communicated, further conversations with infrastructure providers within priority areas should be encouraged.

Stakeholder Survey Questions

1. Has your organisation identified locations that are vulnerable to the impacts of climate change?
If you answered Yes, please tell us:
 - How you did this
 - What types of risks you identified
 - Where you identified them (please provide a grid reference or a detailed location description)
2. Has your organisation already explored the potential for nature restoration to reduce identified climate risks? For example, peatland restoration, woodland creation, natural flood management, SuDs schemes/raingardens.
3. Has your organisation identified any priority locations for nature-based climate adaptation?
If so, where? Please provide a grid reference or a detailed location description.
4. What type of nature restoration do you think is required to address the climate risks your organisation is facing (either identified or anticipated)?
5. Are you already progressing any nature-based climate adaptation projects?
If so, where? Please provide a grid reference or a detailed location description.
6. If you haven't explored the potential for nature restoration to reduce risks yet, would your organisation be interested in collaborating with others to deliver nature restoration for climate adaptation?
If yes, who would be the best person to contact about this? Please provide a name and email address.
7. Would your organisation be able to contribute towards the cost of nature restoration in the prioritised locations?
8. What do you think the blockers are to delivering nature restoration in your priority locations?
For example, funding, knowledge and skills, awareness of options, policy, regulation etc.
9. What has been the driver for the use of nature restoration to address climate risks? For example, policy / regulation, cost, improvements to place, biodiversity or climate duties.
10. Please provide your name and the organisation you have responded on behalf of
Name
Company

Survey respondents

Local authorities

- Stirling Council
- Clackmannanshire Council (x2)
- Aberdeen City Council
- Perth and Kinross Council
- Inverclyde Council
- Midlothian Council
- Aberdeenshire Council
- The Highland Council
- Fife Council
- Dundee City Council
- Glasgow Clyde Valley Green Network (Glasgow City Region)
- North Ayrshire Council

Public bodies / agencies

- The Scottish Parliament
- Historic Environment Scotland
- Forestry and Land Scotland
- SSEN Distribution
- SEPA
- Water Environment Fund (SEPA)
- Scottish Water

NGOs

- Findhorn, Nairn, and Lossie Rivers Trust (x2)
- Bioregioning Tayside
- Learning Through Landscapes
- Tweed Forum
- Loch Lomond and the Trossachs Countryside Trust
- Wester Ross Fisheries Trust
- Morar Salmon Fishery Sub-Board, and Scamadale
- Tweed Forum / Dundee university
- Dee District Salmon Fishery Board
- The Deveron, Bogie and Isla Rivers Charitable Trust
- West Sutherland Fisheries Trust
- Forth Rivers Trust
- The Tweed Foundation
- Fisheries Management Scotland
- Tay Rivers Trust
- Skye and Lochalsh Rivers Trust
- Fife Coast and Countryside Trust
- Kyle of Sutherland Rivers Trust
- River South Esk Catchment Partnership/Angus Council

Landowners

- Edinglassie Estate
- Welbeck Estates

Note: Landowners were not specifically targeted for the survey, though the wide promotion of the survey meant that some did decide to respond to it. Engagement with landowners is a key next step to this project, and they will be involved in the discussions about potential project and partnership development.

Unknown: 6

Survey responses by organisation type: summary information

Priority Landscapes	Organisation type	
<p>Local authorities (13)</p> <p>Who submitted a response</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Stirling Council ○ Clackmannanshire Council (x2) ○ Aberdeen City Council ○ Perth and Kinross Council ○ Inverclyde Council ○ Midlothian Council ○ Aberdeenshire Council ○ The Highland Council ○ Fife Council ○ Dundee City Council ○ Glasgow Clyde Valley green network ○ North Ayrshire Council 	<p>Which types of locations have been identified as being at risk?</p> <p>At various scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Urban areas ○ Specific neighbourhoods ○ Specific assets, infrastructures and the built environment (bridges) ○ Catchment wide ○ Shorelines 	<p>Which types of locations have been identified for nature restoration?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ City regions (districts within city regions) ○ Flood prone zones ○ Whole catchments
<p>Common forms of climate risk</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flooding (9) ○ Erosion (2) ○ Nature depletion (3) ○ Infrastructure (2) ○ Heat in urban areas / lack of shade (2) 	<p>Common forms of nature restoration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tree planting and increasing canopy cover • Natural flood mgmt. • Peat restoration • Woodland creation • Nature based blue/green infrastructure in urban environments including SuDS • Habitat connectivity • Dune restoration 	

Drivers

Policy & regulation: Strong policy and regulation are leading drivers for nature restoration for LAs. Obligations around climate duties push action.

Cost: Cost-effectiveness plays a key role, with nature-based solutions often seen as the most cost-efficient approach compared to engineered solutions.

Opportunities for collaboration and funding: Availability of funding, such as the Peatland Restoration Fund, and support from organizations like the Green Action Trust, enable collaboration on nature restoration projects. This support helps integrate nature-based solutions alongside traditional methods.

Place-based Improvements: For this group there is a focus on improving local places, with clear evidence showing that nature-based interventions directly benefit communities. This is critical in gaining council and community support for such initiatives.

Priority Landscapes	Organisation type	
<p>Public bodies/agencies (7)</p> <p>Who submitted a response</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The Scottish Parliament ○ Historic Environment Scotland ○ Forestry and Land Scotland ○ SSEN Distribution ○ SEPA ○ Water Environment Fund (SEPA) ○ Scottish Water 	<p>Which types of locations have been identified as being at risk?</p> <p>At various scales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ From bespoke (applicable in areas of high archaeological sensitivity) to community scale to catchment level ○ Specific communities: 452 community scale PVAs and 'influencing' areas. Each PVA has been attributed an influencing catchment to embed the catchment / coastal zone approach to flood risk management. ○ Specific assets– sites, properties in care, substations 	<p>Which types of locations have been identified for nature restoration?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Rivers ○ Coasts ○ Parks ○ Forests ○ Peatlands
<p>Common forms of climate risk</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flooding (5) ○ Drought (2) ○ Destabilisation of riverbanks and slopes (2) ○ Erosion (coastal) (1) 	<p>Common forms of nature restoration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Natural flood mgmt ○ Peatland restoration ○ Riparian interventions ○ Dune restoration 	<p>Drivers</p> <p>Duties for public bodies: Key factors include climate change duties for public bodies and public expectation.</p> <p>Biodiversity: A driving factor, possibly related to conservation goals, regulatory compliance, or sustainability efforts.</p> <p>Policy & costs: Focus on securing private investment, improving specific locations and balancing priorities like biodiversity and climate change.</p> <p>Internal policy: Aiming for lower costs than traditional "grey" infrastructure solutions while meeting biodiversity goals and Net Zero carbon targets.</p>

Priority Landscapes	Organisation type	
<p>NGOs (20)</p> <p>Who submitted a response</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Findhorn, Nairn, and Lossie Rivers Trust (x2) o Bioregioning Tayside o Learning Through Landscapes o Tweed Forum o Loch Lomond and the Trossachs Countryside Trust o Wester Ross Fisheries Trust o Morar Salmon Fishery Sub-Board, and Scamadale o Tweed Forum / Dundee university o Dee District Salmon Fishery Board o The Deveron, Bogie and Isla Rivers Charitable Trust o West Sutherland Fisheries Trust o Forth Rivers Trust o The Tweed Foundation o Fisheries Management Scotland o Tay Rivers Trust o Skye and Lochalsh Rivers Trust o Fife Coast and Countryside Trust o Kyle of Sutherland Rivers Trust o River South Esk Catchment Partnership/Angus Council 	<p>Which types of locations have been identified as being at risk?</p> <p>Not something restricted to single locations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Catchment scale with focus on upper reaches and their impacts downstream o City centres o School grounds 	<p>Which types of locations have been identified for nature restoration?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Upland tributaries. o Agricultural lands o Villages o City centres
<p>Common forms of climate risk</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Flooding (12) o Increase in water temperature (9) o Loss of biodiversity / nature depletion (8) o Drought (5) o Erosion (coastal (2) and river (2) (4) o Risks to infrastructure 	<p>Common forms of nature restoration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o River restoration (catchment fertility, improve flow) o Riparian woodland restoration o Woodland creation (upland land management, ancient woodland, reduction in browsers) o Peatland restoration o Wetland creation o Management of non-native invasive species 	
		<p>Drivers</p> <p>Specific species protection: Focus on protecting wild Atlantic salmon and the broader fishery, with an emphasis on ecosystem health as an indicator.</p> <p>Moral responsibility: to address the biodiversity and climate crises.</p> <p>Community impact and economic considerations: Emphasizing the social and economic impact of not addressing biodiversity and climate needs.</p> <p>Funding and collaboration: Opportunistic use of various funding streams to support nature restoration projects.</p> <p>Policy integration and partnership: Successful integration of climate and biodiversity policies through functional, multi-partner collaboration, catchment planning, and land management strategies.</p>

Note: Landowners were not specifically targeted for the survey, though the wide promotion of the survey meant that some did decide to respond to it. Engagement with landowners is a key next step to this project, and they will be involved in the discussions about potential project and partnership development.

Priority Landscapes	Organisation type	
<h3 data-bbox="237 371 472 408">Landowners (2)</h3> <p data-bbox="237 435 551 462">Who submitted a response</p> <ul data-bbox="237 496 439 547" style="list-style-type: none"><li data-bbox="237 496 439 520">○ Edinglassie Estate<li data-bbox="237 523 439 547">○ Welbeck Estates	<h3 data-bbox="913 376 1541 435">Which types of locations have been identified as being at risk?</h3> <p data-bbox="913 475 1088 499">At the estate level</p> <ul data-bbox="913 531 1059 582" style="list-style-type: none"><li data-bbox="913 531 1059 555">○ Catchments<li data-bbox="913 558 1059 582">○ Waterways	<h3 data-bbox="1601 379 2013 438">Which types of locations have been identified for nature restoration?</h3> <ul data-bbox="1601 475 1753 526" style="list-style-type: none"><li data-bbox="1601 475 1753 499">○ Catchments<li data-bbox="1601 502 1753 526">○ Waterways
<h3 data-bbox="232 847 577 871">Common forms of climate risk</h3> <ul data-bbox="232 906 557 981" style="list-style-type: none"><li data-bbox="232 906 342 930">○ Flooding<li data-bbox="232 957 557 981">○ Increase in water temperatures	<h3 data-bbox="927 884 1352 908">Common forms of nature restoration</h3> <ul data-bbox="943 983 1368 1121" style="list-style-type: none"><li data-bbox="943 983 1279 1007">○ Remeandering of water courses<li data-bbox="943 1010 1368 1062">○ Installations of ponds/floodplains to slow water movement<li data-bbox="943 1066 1167 1090">○ Riparian woodlands<li data-bbox="943 1093 1167 1117">○ Peatland restoration	<h3 data-bbox="1601 659 1693 683">Drivers</h3> <p data-bbox="1592 711 2051 735">Urgency: observing changes happening on land</p> <p data-bbox="1592 767 2040 874">Availability of funding: drives actions like tree planting and blocking ditches. Current funding is believed to be too stringent and doesn't allow for experimentation.</p>

Priority Landscapes	Organisation type	
<p>Unknown (6)</p> <p>Who submitted a response</p> <p>NA</p>	<p>Which types of locations have been identified as being at risk?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Target neighbourhoods ○ Urban areas (x2) ○ Areas identified through SEPA flood risk mapping 	<p>Which types of locations have been identified for nature restoration?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Rivers ○ Urban areas in connection to other projects like active travel programmes and Liveable neighbourhoods
<p>Common forms of climate risk</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Flooding (5) ○ Increase in water temperatures ○ Poor health outcomes ○ Coastal erosion ○ Biodiversity loss 	<p>Common forms of nature restoration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Peatland restoration (2x) ○ Grassland restoration ○ Wetland restoration ○ SuDS ○ Peatland restoration ○ Tree planting 	<p>Drivers</p>

Key Informant Interview Questions

Section 1: Background information

1. Can you tell us more about you, your role and the organisation you work for. How does your company operate?
2. Where do you operate (geographically)?
3. What general challenges is your organisation facing now? Do you think any relate specifically to climate change?

Section 2: climate risk

1. How do you currently understand climate risk?
2. What are your highest priority risks? How were these identified? Where are they located?
 - a. Did you have sufficient information to build your understanding of climate risk?
3. Are these risks known and shared by others within the organisation? How are they used?
4. As an infrastructure operator, we're keen to understand where you have assets or plan to have assets in the near future. We understand some of these locations you cannot share but can you reflect on locations of assets, climate risk and any proposals you have to mitigating these risks?
 - a. Are there specific types of geographic areas or landscapes that you believe are vulnerable to climate risks (ie urban areas, specific communities, a specific river)
5. Do you understand the cascading impacts of these risks?
6. Do you report these risks publicly? [Public Bodies Climate Changes Duties Reporting, ISSB]
 - a. If not, why?

Section 3: Nature based solutions

We are particularly interested in understanding how your organisation is prioritising investment in and using nature-based solutions to mitigate climate risks. We define nature based solutions as actions that protect, manage, or restore natural ecosystems.

1. In your organisation, what types of nature restoration / nature-based solutions have been identified?
 - a. How many of these have been implemented?
 - b. In which types of landscapes have these been implemented?
 - c. At what scale?
 - d. Are you doing this in collaboration with others? Who?
2. What drives/motivates you to use nature restoration projects to address climate risk? (examples could include improving places, available funding policy/ regulation, cost effectiveness of NbS solutions, concern about a specific species)

3. What are the challenges you face in implementing NbS?
4. How are your climate adaptation and nature projects funded?
5. If your organisation willing to contribute financially to landscape scale nature projects with others?

Section 4: Close

1. What might incentivise more action in this area?
2. Is there anything else you would like to reflect on?

Key Informant Interview organisations:

Scottish Water, Climate Change Adaptation Technical Lead

Scottish Water, Business Strategy and Climate Change Manager

SSE Distribution, Sustainability Analyst

Scottish Government , Sustainability Manager

NHS, Sustainability Manager (Adaptation and Resilience)

Transport Scotland, Climate Change Manager

Network Rail, Weather Resilience and Climate Change Adaptation Strategy Manager

Scottish Gas Networks were invited to interview and initially accepted, however declined as they were unable to agree to the interview consent form conditions.

Key Informant Interviews: summary information

Priority Landscapes	Key Informant Interview 1	
<h2 data-bbox="219 347 555 400">Network Rail</h2> <p data-bbox="219 427 439 459">Background info</p> <p data-bbox="219 491 842 571">Four delivery units across Scotland (East = Edinburgh, Perth up to highlands) and West (Motherwell and Glasgow, East of)</p> <p data-bbox="219 603 842 715">Working to understand what drainage they have in relation to their infrastructure; what state it is in and how to design it out to anticipate climate change to SEPA guidelines.</p> <p data-bbox="219 746 842 858">They are seeing a change. The challenge is understanding existing system and get it up to a level that's manageable to then be able to identify where resilience is needed.</p>	<p data-bbox="887 347 1559 379">Priority risks and where they have been identified</p> <p data-bbox="887 387 1559 467">Flooding, wind, extreme cold, frost & erosion <i>"There's something at risk everywhere. There wouldn't be a catchment that the rail runs through that isn't a concern."</i></p> <p data-bbox="887 499 1559 651">Cited, Edinburgh to Glasgow Mainline, East Coast Mainline, West Coast Mainline, Perth to Inverness (Highland Mainline), West Highland Line (including branch lines to Oban, Fort William and Mallaig) as well as West Highlands and Bridge of Orchy - routes characterised by bounding steep-sided/mountainous topography and at risk of erosion.</p> <p data-bbox="887 683 1435 715">Specific locations of existing investment</p> <p data-bbox="887 738 1559 850">Glasgow North Electrics, Blair Atholl to Dalwhinnie, Fife, Perth and Arbroath, Winchburgh Tunnel, Structures East - Edinburgh, E&G, ECML, and Borders, West Coast and Edinburgh to Glasgow Mainlines, Kilmarnock</p>	<p data-bbox="1585 347 1921 403">Funding for nature based solutions</p> <p data-bbox="1585 443 2033 611">In terms of risk, drainage score is very high. Driver would be condition or performance issues that needs rectifying, rather than a climate challenge. NbS work would come from the drainage budget.</p> <p data-bbox="1585 643 2033 722">Have the appetite but need to prove the business case with recognisable benefit to the organisation.</p> <p data-bbox="1585 746 1809 770">Incentivising action</p> <p data-bbox="1585 802 2033 858">The business case for the use of NbS needs to be stronger.</p>
<p data-bbox="219 906 842 978">Understanding of climate risk and areas of vulnerability</p> <p data-bbox="219 1018 730 1074">686 climate risks identified - most based on performance issues</p> <p data-bbox="219 1106 842 1241">Agnostic to location. How climate interacted with assets - breaking down the infrastructure into components (ditches, culverts, pipes) - looked at the ways these could be impacted. Downside of this was that it was not spatial.</p> <p data-bbox="219 1273 842 1321">Now conducting a spatial climate risk assessment from which areas of vulnerability can be identified.</p>	<p data-bbox="887 898 1480 930">Reflections of use of Nature based solutions</p> <p data-bbox="887 954 1559 1034">Early days in efforts to use nature to address challenges. Access poses a challenge. Sometimes NbS needs more land and are not as robust as they are need to be.</p> <p data-bbox="887 1058 1559 1169">Internally pushing designers to consider NbS. Integration is about behaviour/culture change again where they have always focused on fixing the problem inside the railway corridor, they now must think outside of it.</p> <p data-bbox="887 1193 1559 1321">There is a need for good examples of NbS within the network. To promote this takes time. They own very little of the land to needed to implement some of these on. Believe costs can be prohibitive, so working with lineside neighbours and stakeholders must be imperative.</p>	<p data-bbox="1585 890 2033 1169">In an engineering firm, internal stakeholders need more technical knowledge and data that demonstrates the success of such interventions to provide reassurance that nature is a suitable and effective alternative to a solution that has already been defined. This collective knowledge and understanding needs to be mainstreamed.</p> <p data-bbox="1585 1201 2033 1281">Key driver is safety. If there is any strong concern about network safety, it will not get implemented.</p>

Priority Landscapes	Key informant interview 2 & 3	
<p>NHS Assure + Scot Gov</p> <p>Background info</p> <p>Part of the climate change, sustainability and environment team of NHS Assure which belongs to National Service Scotland (a specialist national board). Help regional 22 health boards (14 territorial and 8 special boards) update their risk assessments, adaptation plans, guidance for implementing adaptation measures. Currently enhancing their climate mapping tool which boards can access online. Autonomous in a sense but the Scot Gov can encourage them to move in a certain direction. NSS have their own sustainability team.</p> <p>Scot Gov representative looking at decarbonisation of NHS and infrastructure.</p>	<p>Priority risks and where they have been identified</p> <p>Flooding, combined climatic effects (high winds, storms), downpours, prolonged periods of heat & cold spells. Organise hazards based on risks to; infrastructure, essential supplies, equipment, access. Risks are managed from a resilience point of view.</p> <p>More populated areas, greater Glasgow and Clyde (estates and population). Western Isle and Shetland – access is more difficult. There are so many ways to see vulnerability (age of the estate, population, older population, older population and level of complexity) - cannot say which area. Ayshire & Arran score highest on the Average Risk Exposure Score per NHS board (but this is self-reported).</p>	<p>Funding for nature based solutions</p> <p>Need to show good value for money.</p>
<p>Understanding of climate risk and areas of vulnerability</p> <p>Each NHS board has identified risks that could impact their assets and service provision, recognising a total of 952 potential climate change impacts across all twenty-two NHS boards. Currently, mitigation is prioritised over adaptation, because there are national goals (Scottish Adaption plan). Adaptation its not goal orientated.</p> <p>Existing climate change risk assessments are very high level – some boards specify specific assets, others haven't. Assessments are subjected to local expertise. Impact scores aren't comparable across boards.</p>	<p>Reflections of use of Nature based solutions</p> <p>Few focused reflections on NbS. Aware that its effective and beneficial but little evidence on how it builds on existing green spaces and biodiversity targets.</p> <p>Current priorities include how green networks (walking, cycling) and greenspaces around hospitals are created around hospitals. Referenced the use of SuDS.</p> <p>Currently working on developing an adaptation planning guidance which might include NbS as an adaptation measure but more evidence on proposed benefits needed.</p>	<p>Incentivising action</p> <p><i>"Sometimes it feels like a bit of work here and a bit of work there. A concept at catchment scale will be interesting"</i></p> <p>Knowledge and awareness of the potential impacts of climate change and the benefits of implementing adaptation measures can motivate people to start progressing them but more examples are needed.</p> <p>Seeing examples from other countries is an inspiration.</p>

Priority Landscapes	Key informant interview 4	
<h2 data-bbox="219 300 672 355">SSEN Distribution</h2> <h3 data-bbox="219 379 448 411">Background info</h3> <p data-bbox="219 435 835 523">Distribution network operators. Deliver power to 3.9 m customers in UK, 792k in Scotland. In Scotland, operate in the north – from about Stirling upward.</p>	<h3 data-bbox="891 300 1429 355">Priority risks and where they have been identified</h3> <p data-bbox="891 387 1417 419">flood risk, river, pluvial and coastal sea flooding.</p> <p data-bbox="891 443 1529 667">Top three (with the highest risk rating in 2023 and 2050) include substations affected by river flooding due to increased winter rainfall, by pluvial (flash) flooding due to increased rainstorms in summer and winter and by sea flooding due to increased sea levels and/or tidal surges, followed by overhead line conductors affected by temperature, and underground cable systems affected by increase in ground temperature, reducing ratings.</p> <p data-bbox="891 691 1507 802">Grid and primary substations are protected from flood risk. Identifying which ones are high risk sites are from anecdotal evidence - not a thorough assessment done using flood risk maps.</p>	<h3 data-bbox="1574 300 1921 355">Funding for nature based solutions</h3> <p data-bbox="1574 387 2033 659">In current biz plan they do have commitments to NbS which have been funded for but it's challenging to make the business case for NbS to Ofgem. Funding is a quarter of what they were originally asking for. Need to build a strong consumer value proposition to demonstrate how its funded, its role in carbon removal, green job creation, volunteer hours.</p>
<h3 data-bbox="219 850 835 922">Understanding of climate risk and areas of vulnerability</h3> <p data-bbox="219 954 846 1034">Have a Climate Resilience Strategy but understanding is piecemeal. Worked with the Energy Networks Association to identify 15 direct risks to network assets.</p> <p data-bbox="219 1066 846 1257">There is a GIS exercise being done with assets and risk register (beyond grid and primary substations to include secondary substations) - in the process of doing this, need to hire skills. Held in a Sharepoint and excel document- identifying sites to do flood risk assessments for. Currently doing this for Scotland- dependent on next round of funding.</p>	<h3 data-bbox="891 850 1485 882">Reflections of use of Nature based solutions</h3> <p data-bbox="891 914 1541 1026">Currently, NbS is mainly being used for carbon reduction. Have 400 hectares of peatland restoration in Scotland. This might change. Target of 129 hectares of woodland creation. 14 hectares of seagrass restoration.</p> <p data-bbox="891 1050 1541 1129">Nature4Networks- a small set of specific distribution assets and use cases such as flood protection for existing primary substations or new substation construction.</p> <p data-bbox="891 1137 1406 1273">Experimenting with</p> <ul data-bbox="902 1161 1395 1273" style="list-style-type: none"> • Linear woodlands to screen overhead lines • Thorny planting around wood poles • SuDS to prevent assets flooding • Bioswales to capture oil 	<h3 data-bbox="1574 691 1798 722">Incentivising action</h3> <p data-bbox="1574 730 2022 1098">Regulated industry is challenging as accountants don't know how to account for investments in nature. Ofgem are an economic regulator, and processes don't account for social and environmental benefits. There needs to be guidance from Ofgem and IFRS. NbS often lands as an Opex cost neglecting the need for ongoing management and maintenance. Will be publishing their own document on regulatory challenges. Action to ensure procurement services are open and fair is needed to widen the pool of appropriate responses to climate risks.</p> <p data-bbox="1574 1121 2022 1281">There are broader nature market challenges – availability of suitable options, additionality is confusing. There's a lack of skills people, resources and knowledge. This is a new area and there is a lot of learning on the job.</p>

Priority Landscapes	Key Informant Interview 4	
<h2 data-bbox="224 303 604 359">Scottish Water</h2> <h3 data-bbox="224 383 448 414">Background info</h3> <p data-bbox="224 446 851 558">Working to mainstream climate change adaptation to ensure organisation are taking sufficient new behaviour change in operations and asset investment so that they are prepared for climate change.</p> <p data-bbox="224 582 851 646">Work at a national scale. Manage 400+ water sources across Scotland and 50,000km of water networks</p> <p data-bbox="224 670 851 726">Move beyond catchment partnerships, with small pieces of funding from different sources.</p>	<h3 data-bbox="907 303 1444 367">Priority risks and where they have been identified</h3> <p data-bbox="907 391 1523 486">Deteriorating raw water quality, <u>wetter</u> winters that cause flooding, variable rainfall patterns, more frequent storms, sea rise and erosion.</p> <p data-bbox="907 502 1523 646">Many risks are spread across the country. Scottish Water have not identified specific geographical hotspots. The east coast is of concern which has been exacerbated by shifts in population from West to East as well as lower rain fall.</p>	<h3 data-bbox="1568 303 1792 335">Funding for NbS</h3> <p data-bbox="1568 359 1971 446">Trying to make the case through customer financing and government borrowing.</p> <p data-bbox="1568 470 2004 598">Still experience barriers to making the business case. Hard to outline the certainty of outcome. Lacking information needed or the cost benefit assessment.</p> <hr/> <h3 data-bbox="1568 654 1803 686">Incentivising action</h3> <p data-bbox="1568 710 2027 901">Articulated a strong need for national policy alignment, shared governance and buy in with an alliance from SEPA, Scot Gov, <u>NatureScot</u> and local authorities to agree areas of focus. Without which, there is a risk of fragmented restoration plans that do not deliver strong benefits.</p>
<h3 data-bbox="224 853 851 933">Understanding of climate risk and areas of vulnerability</h3> <p data-bbox="224 957 851 1021">27 key risks are outlined in the Scottish Water Adaptation Plan based on 2°C and 4°C warming.</p> <p data-bbox="224 1045 851 1189">Looks at risks on environment (availability and quality of water), assets (performance and reliability), customers and communities (meeting future needs), people (skills and capabilities) and suppliers and interdependencies (global impacts).</p>	<h3 data-bbox="907 853 1500 885">Reflections of use of Nature based solutions</h3> <p data-bbox="907 901 1534 1021">Nature based solutions are not new at <u>Scottish Water</u> but it was suggested that current initiatives are not being implemented at the scale or pace required to adapt to climate change impacts.</p> <p data-bbox="907 1045 1400 1077">Two main areas they are undertaking NbS:</p> <ol data-bbox="907 1077 1534 1268" style="list-style-type: none"> 1. At a catchment management perspective - providing multiple benefits to protect water quality but also carbon sequestration, biodiversity benefits in open catchments through peatland 2. Separation of stormwater/rainwater out of combined <u>waste water</u> networks through use of blue/green infrastructure in urban environments 	<p data-bbox="1568 917 2027 1165">Encouragement to plan over longer time scales. River based management planning is currently looked at in six-year cycles but this is not adequate for climate adaptation. Need to see 25 years out in terms of future climate risk to drive thinking about what needs to change now to make regenerative catchments exist in future.</p> <p data-bbox="1568 1189 1982 1268">Build the evidence base of customer benefits and better articulate the multiple benefits achieved by <u>NbS</u>.</p>

Priority Landscapes	Key informant perspective 6	
<p>Transport Scotland</p> <p>Background info</p> <p>Transport Scotland’s Approach to Climate Change Adaptation and Resilience (ACCAR), outlines the key climate risks affecting Scotland’s transport system and sets out our strategic outcomes for Road, Rail, Aviation and Maritime transport networks.</p> <p>Supports the delivery of climate change adaptation as well as aviation and maritime sectors.</p>	<p>Priority risks and where they have been identified</p> <p>Land associated with the Trunk Road Network</p> <p>The trunk road and motorway network is 3,507 km (2,179 miles) long, including slip roads and roundabouts. It has a gross asset value of over £20.8 billion and represents 6% of the total Scottish road network.</p> <p>Transport Scotland landscape policy is applicable to both maintenance issues and the delivery of new schemes. Responsible for the preparation and delivery of the following landscape information: a unit-wide landscape strategy; an annual landscape development plan; an annual report</p>	<p>Funding for nature based solutions</p>
<p>Understanding of climate risk and areas of vulnerability</p> <p>7 key climate risks that relate to transport infrastructure: Risks to infrastructure networks (water, energy, transport, ICT) from cascading failures; risks to infrastructure services from river, surface water and groundwater flooding; Risks to infrastructure services from coastal flooding and erosion; Risks to bridges and pipelines from flooding and erosion; Risks to networks from slope and embankment failure; Risks to subterranean and surface infrastructure from subsidence; Risks to transport from high and low temperatures, high winds, lightning</p>	<p>Reflections of use of Nature based solutions</p> <p>No explicit mention of NbS in climate adaptation plan. Outlines aims to integrate green infrastructure solutions into transport developments related to risks to infrastructure and services from river, surface water and groundwater flooding.</p>	<p>Incentivising action</p>

Sustainability Reporting / Climate Disclosure Analysis

Organisation	Amount of land	Have they done some type of publicly available reporting on climate risks?	In this do they share information about areas of risk?	What adaptation measures (if any) do they mention?	Use of nature restoration
Scottish Water	Responsible for 23,000 hectares	<p>Yes</p> <p>TCFS https://www.scottishwater.co.uk/-/media/ScottishWater/Document-Hub/Key-Publications/Annual-Reports/Scottish-Water-Annual-Report-2024.pdf (pg 39)</p> <p>https://indd.adobe.com/view/d63df175-559e-4ec7-a2b5-8227596a710e (pg 11)</p>	Loch Katrine		<p>None explicitly outlined in TCFD but Biodiversity report published in line with duty under Natural Environment Act 2011 details plan for nature restoration focused on natural capital</p> <p>https://www.scottishwater.co.uk/-/media/ScottishWater/Document-Hub/Key-Publications/Energy-and-Sustainability/211223Biodiversityreport23FINAL.pdf</p>

<p>SSEN Distribution</p>		<p>Yes</p> <p>15 risks identified – mainly risks to assets due to temperature increases, drought and flooding</p> <p>https://www.ssen.co.uk/globalassets/library/climate-change-adaptation-docs/ssen-distribution-fourth-climate-change-adaptation-report.pdf</p> <p>Environmental report: https://www.ssen.co.uk/globalassets/library/environment-report-2024/ssen-distribution---annual-environmental-report-2024--final-web-v17.pdf</p> <p>https://www.sse.com/sustainability/</p>	<p>No but developing spatial (GIS) maps of risks of assets to flooding</p>		<p>Yes but specific to carbon removal - aim to plant 258 hectares of native woodland and restore 522 hectares of peatland in our licence areas, which are expected to remove up to 65,000 tCO2e by 2045</p> <p>Now working to Identify where there are issues faced by networks which could be addressed by a Nature-based Solutions (NbS) approach.</p> <p>https://www.ssen.co.uk/about-ssen/sustainability/#:~:text=We%20have%20an%20ambitious%20sustainability%20strategy%20outlining%20our,own%20environmental%20impact%20in%20a%20transparent%2C%20credible%20way</p> <p>Nature4Networks - Ofgem innovation fund exploring the use of nature-based solutions to safeguard electricity networks (https://smarter.energynetworks.org/projects/10105122/)</p>
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Prioritising Catchments for Nature Restoration: Supplementary Material.

<p>Historic Environment Scotland</p>		<p>No Climate adaption plan to be developed</p>	<p>No</p>		<p>Noted as a driver in survey response Nature restoration mentioned in Climate Action Plan in which is key part of KPI 5 'Increasingly lead the sector in climate change action' in Annual Report.</p>
<p>Forestry and Land Scotland</p>	<p>9% of Scotland</p>	<p>No A full strategic climate change risk assessment for FLS has not been carried out Last published Annual sustainability report in 2021 - https://forestryandland.gov.scot/media/iabkzx0r/fls-annual-sustainability-report-2020-2021.pdf</p>	<p>No</p>		
<p>Scottish Power Energy Networks (SPEN)</p>		<p>Yes 35 risks were identified, which have been separated out depending on the asset or assets the risk is impacting. https://www.spenergynetworks.co.uk/userfiles/file/Climate-Resilience-Strategy-RIIO-T3-Business-plan-SP-Energy-Networks.pdf</p>	<p>Possibly? Need more info In the short term, SPT will work with local climate adaptation partners to identify five priority areas and develop project plans by the end of 2027 for</p>	<p>Organised by three types (soft, green and hard)</p>	<p>Yes and budgeted for https://www.spenergynetworks.co.uk/userfiles/file/SP_Energy_Networks_Action_Plan_for_Nature.pdf</p>

Prioritising Catchments for Nature Restoration: Supplementary Material.

			<p>implementation by the end of 2031 – Refer to the SPEN T3 Environmental Action Plan</p> <p>In the future we plan to carry out location specific assessments to take in to account the variety of risks that are impinging on our assets</p>		
Network Rail		<p>Yes</p> <p>https://www.networkrail.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/Network-Rail-4th-Adaptation-Report-Dec-2024.pdf</p> <p>https://www.networkrail.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/Network-Rail-Third-Adaptation-Report-December-2021.pdf</p>	<p>No - but developing spatial analysis to be delivered in March</p>	<p>https://www.networkrail.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/Scotlands-Railway-CP7-Climate-Ready-WRCCA-Plan.pdf</p>	

Prioritising Catchments for Nature Restoration: Supplementary Material.

<p>Transport Scotland (regional transport partnerships)</p>		<p>Most Transport Partnerships and IJBs have not undertaken a risk assessment or only with respect to a single issue. This may be due to corporate adaptation risks being addressed by the host body taking responsibility for addressing direct risks to occupied estate and shared assets and services (Public Bodies Climate Changes Duties Reporting 22- 23)</p>	<p>No</p>		
<p>NHS Scotland</p>		<p>Yes https://www.nss.nhs.scot/media/5784/asr500-002-report-of-ccras-and-ap-v1-jan-25.pdf</p>	<p>No</p>	<p>Weather monitoring and temperature management to the implementation of nature-based solutions</p>	
<p>Scottish Gas Networks</p>		<p>Yes 43 potential risks pertaining to asset management and physical security, health & safety and environment & climate change https://www.sgn.co.uk/sites/default/files/media-entities/documents/2022-01/SGN-ARP3-1221_0.pdf</p>	<p>Northeast coast of Scotland (sea level rise) Across Scotland (flooding)</p>		<p>https://www.sgn.co.uk/news/improving-and-protecting-biodiversity-our-sites</p>

Prioritising Catchments for Nature Restoration: Supplementary Material.

<p>Local authorities</p>		<p>While every local authority has carried out some form of risk assessment and 53% of the sector has done so to a comprehensive or advanced degree, nearly half (47%) of local authority reports indicate that only single-issue risks have been considered, i.e. flooding. (Public Bodies Climate Changes Duties Reporting 22- 23)</p>	<p>Not enough data</p>	<p>Not enough data</p>	
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